

A Veterinarian's take on World Tuberculosis Day (24th March)

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Abstract

Tuberculosis (TB) is a chronic disease affecting millions worldwide. Every year 24th March is celebrated as World Tuberculosis Day to raise awareness on this deadly disease to strengthen control and eradication of this disease. Globally, just eight countries have two-third of human TB cases and India has the highest burden of TB cases in the world. One of component of tuberculosis is zoonotic TB caused by *Mycobacterium bovis*, which is often left to be discussed. In this article, the authors have highlighted the present status of tuberculosis globally and contribution of veterinarians in control of TB especially zoonotic TB.

Introduction

Tuberculosis (TB) is a chronic debilitating granulomatous infection and is one of the deadly infectious diseases of humans as well as animals. The disease is known from ancient times and, paradoxically, despite the availability of preventive and control measures, the disease is still present in significant numbers in many countries of the world. Ironically – India – has the highest incidence of TB cases in the world.

As per Global TB Report 2021 (WHO), in 2020, 9.9 million cases of TB were active globally. About one-quarter of these cases (2.6 million) are in India alone. In India, there has been a decrease of 13% in TB cases from 2015-2020; however, TB-associated deaths have seen a rise of 7.3%. About two-thirds of the global TB cases are in eight countries viz., India (26%), China (8.5%), Indonesia (8.4%), Philippines (6.0%), Pakistan (5.8%), Nigeria (4.6%), Bangladesh (3.6%) and South Africa (3.3%). Human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) has further exaggerated the situation of TB and India is the second country (after South Africa) in the world having highest TB cases in HIV patients. Further, Covid-19 pandemic has severely impacted TB control and elimination. Globally, due to Covid-19 pandemic situation, TB notifications in 2020 tumbled to 5.8 million from 7.1 million of 2019.

History of World Tuberculosis Day

TB is known from ancient times and has been documented by various names in history such as phthisis, consumption, scrofula and Pott's disease. It was J.L. Schonlein who suggested the name of 'tuberculosis' due to tubercles formation in clinical disease. The first-time isolation of pathogen was done by Robert Koch, who announced the isolation on 24th March, 1882. Every year 24th March is celebrated as World Tuberculosis Day in commemoration of this discovery. This year the theme of World Tuberculosis Day is - 'Invest to End TB. Save Lives', indicating the need to invest higher resources to combat the TB epidemic especially in the aftermath of Covid-19.

Tuberculosis in humans

TB in humans is caused by the acid-fast bacilli called *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* which is a part of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* complex. The complex includes *M. tuberculosis*, *M. bovis*, *M. africanum*, *M. caprae*, *M. microti*, *M. canettii* and *M. pinnipedii*, although *M. tuberculosis*, *M. africanum*, *M. bovis* and *M. caprae* are the major TB causing species in humans. *M. tuberculosis* is quite host-specific infecting mainly humans; although occasional cases in other species are reported. *M. africanum* is responsible for TB in humans in Central and Western Africa. *M. bovis* is the species mainly infecting cattle and other animals but infects humans also. In fact, it is the most important *Mycobacterium* species causing transmission of TB from animals to humans i.e. zoonotic TB. For *M. caprae*, the primary host species is goats, while cases in cattle and humans are also reported.

Disease in humans

The disease caused by *M. tuberculosis* is mainly airborne, infecting respiratory system of host. The pathogenesis involves chronic granulomatous inflammatory response leading to tubercles formation. If the infection is contained at the site by the inflammatory response, the infection doesn't spread further in the body and the host doesn't transmit the pathogen to other individuals. Such a case is called 'closed case'. However, if the infection spreads in the body, extrapulmonary TB occurs leading to TB of skin (scrofula), spine (Pott's disease) and CNS. As *Mycobacterium* has cell envelope rich in mycolic acids, the entry of drugs is a challenge; therefore, the treatment of TB requires administration of selected drugs for a long time period.

Significance of *M. bovis* in causing TB in humans

As *M. bovis* is the main etiological agent responsible for zoonotic TB in humans, it becomes imperative to target *M. bovis* infection in animals to circumvent the transmission to humans. India has world's largest cattle and buffalo population (about 300 million) and as per

a systematic meta-analysis, the prevalence of bovine TB is estimated to be 7.3% i.e. about 21.8 million cattle (Srinivasan *et al.*, 2018), which is a concern for veterinary sector as well as public health agencies.

M. bovis infection in cattle is known as bovine TB. Bovine TB is a chronic debilitating granulomatous disease in cattle and many other species such as sheep, goats, horses and many wild ruminants. The disease is characterized by chronic cough (in case of respiratory TB), emaciation, cachexia and weight loss in animals, hide bound condition, fever followed by hyperthermia.

The significance of *M. bovis* in causing zoonotic TB in humans has been reported globally. In USA, 1.4% of annual humans TB cases are accounted to *M. bovis*. In 2010, it is estimated the *M. bovis* infected human TB cases amounted to be 1,21,268 globally (WHO). In India, the transmission of *M. bovis* to humans is well reported. In a study in Central India, 301 human blood samples from different human populations were analysed using polymerase chain reaction. 35 samples (11.6%) were positive for *M. bovis*. The study finds the consumption of raw milk as a risk factor for *M. bovis* positivity (Bapat *et al.*, 2017). Prasad *et al.* (2005) have reported about 9% of human TB patients to be positive for *M. bovis*. The large data on *M. bovis* in TB patients in India is lacking. This is because of absence of routine surveillance system targeting *M. bovis* in human TB cases. Majority of *M. bovis* transmission cases in humans are foodborne and not airborne, leading to extrapulmonary tuberculosis cases which are often undiagnosed or misdiagnosed. Human to human aerosol transmission of *M. bovis* is a rare phenomenon. Infection of *M. bovis* in humans is a challenge as *M. bovis* is resistant to pyrazinamide which is one of the first-line drugs used for treatment of TB in humans.

Transmission of *M. bovis* from cattle to humans

The transmission of *M. bovis* from cattle to humans involves following routes of transmission:

- Foodborne: Food is the major vehicle for transmission of *M. bovis* to humans. *M. bovis* is shed in the milk and thus consumption of raw milk/unpasteurized milk or inadequately boiled milk is the major route of transmission. Other risky food items are dairy products made from unpasteurized milk. Consumption of inadequately cooked meat is also a risk for transmission.
- Airborne: Although the Airborne transmission of *M. bovis* to humans is limited, transmission among close contacts to animals is reported.

Role of veterinarians in control of zoonotic TB

Control of *M. bovis* infection in humans primarily depends upon the control of infection in animals. Thus, veterinarians have a major role to control zoonotic TB in humans. This also indicates that zoonotic TB is a perfect example demanding interventions under ‘One Health’ preview.

Veterinarians are the first-line professionals who directly come in contact with the tuberculosis positive animals and thus play a major role in the diagnosis and control of disease. The veterinarians can contribute in the following ways in control of zoonotic TB:

i. **Diagnosis of *M. bovis* infection in animals:** *M. bovis* infection in cattle and other animals is a chronic progressive disease, although sometimes acute course leading to miliary TB may occur. The animal becomes weak and emaciated. As aerosols are the major route of transmission among cattle, the clinical picture involves respiratory system (pulmonary tuberculosis) leading to inflammatory granuloma formation in the lungs. It is called primary foci. Primary foci seldom heals and the infectious agent spreads within host body through circulatory system and lymphatics leading to granuloma formation in other organs such as pleura, peritoneum, liver, kidney, spleen, bones, mammary glands, reproductive tract and CNS. The veterinarians can help in diagnosis of disease by:

- **Suspecting an animal based upon the clinical signs:** suspicion in itself is a way to prevent the spread of disease. Suspicion will be of help even if the diagnostic facilities are not available at the point of action. Veterinarian can inform the owners about the disease suspected and the risk of transmission to animal owners, thereby impacting the control of zoonotic TB, although indirectly.
- **Diagnosis by tuberculin test:** wherever facilities are available, diagnosis by acid-fast staining and tuberculin test can help in definitive diagnosis of bovine TB. Acid-fast staining on respiratory tract excretions is a routine staining method. Tuberculin test is a delayed type hypersensitivity test for testing of TB in individual animals. In Single Intradermal (SID) tuberculin test, purified protein derivative (PPD) of *M. bovis* is intradermally injected at mid neck, caudal fold of tail or vulvar lips. The sites are examined after 72 hrs for signs of inflammation and edema at the inoculation site. As SID can give false positive results in case of infections with *Mycobacteria* other than *M. bovis* due to cross-reaction of antigens, comparative intradermal tuberculin test is done which involves the inoculation of *M. bovis* PPD and *M. avium* PPD on the same side of neck. If the inflammation at the *M. bovis* PPD site is greater than *M. avium* site, the animal is confirmed to be infected with *M. bovis*.

- ii. **Awareness on zoonotic TB among animal owners:** Veterinarians should aware the animal owners on the zoonotic TB and transmission through raw milk/unpasteurized milk and improperly boiled milk, meat and their products. Veterinarians should promote appropriate cooking of foods of animal origin to prevent transmission of TB and other zoonotic diseases from animals to humans.

Conclusions

Tuberculosis is widely present in many parts of the world including India. Zoonotic TB has significant impact on burden of TB in the world. Every year we celebrate World Tuberculosis Day (24th March) to strive our efforts to control this deadly disease. Veterinarians should understand the diagnosis of TB in animals and aware animal owners on ways to prevent transmission from animals to humans.

References

- Bapat et al. 2019. Prevalence of zoonotic tuberculosis and associated risk factors in Central Indian populations. *Journal of Epidemiology and Global Health*, 7:4, 277–283.
- Global tuberculosis report 2021. Geneva: World Health Organization; 2021.
- Olea-Popelka et al. 2017. Zoonotic tuberculosis in human beings caused by *Mycobacterium bovis*-a call for action. *Lancet Infectious Diseases*, 17(1):e21-e25. doi: 10.1016/S1473-3099(16)30139-6.
- Srinivasan et al. 2018. Prevalence of Bovine Tuberculosis in India: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Transboundary and Emerging Diseases*, 65:1627–1640.